

ASSESSMENT OF TRANSLATION QUALITY AND LANGUAGE
COMPLEXITY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7481721>

Nuritdinova Yorkinoy Abdulkhoshim kizi
Andijan Institute of Agriculture and Agro technologies

Annotation: *Regulatory requirements for translation quality make sense only in relation to a certain type of text and certain conditions of translation activity. It would be fundamentally wrong to use the same criteria for evaluating the translation of a tabloid novel and a highly artistic literary work, the translation of an opera libretto and a patent certificate.*

Key words: *Effective communication, quality, linguistic, knowledge, speech, evaluating, translation.*

Translation is the creation of an equivalent text in another language that is not based on the original text in one language, but is equivalent to the original in a communicative sense. In order to translate well, knowledge of two languages is not enough. In order to fully fulfill the communicative function of translation, to ensure that the translation text makes the same impression on the recipient as the original text, it is necessary to know the laws of translation, clearly understand its requirements for translation and for the translator.

The most objective criterion for describing the results of a translator's activity is the equivalence of the translation to the original.

Translation quality – the results of the translation process, which are determined by the degree of its compliance with the translation norm and the nature of involuntary or conscious deviations from this norm.

The quality of translation depends on:

- ❖ the degree of semantic proximity of the translation to the original;
- ❖ genre and stylistic attributes of the original and translated texts;
- ❖ pragmatic factors that influence the choice of translation option.
- ❖ These aspects of translation:
 - ❖ they are normative in nature;
 - ❖ define the translator's strategy and criteria for evaluating the translation.
- ❖ In practice, criticism of translations is based on an intuitive understanding of the genre and stylistic norm:
 - ❖ translation of a work of fiction is evaluated according to its literary merits;
 - ❖ technical translation – based on terminology correctness;
 - ❖ ad translation – based on its effectiveness.
- ❖ 3. For a number of practical purposes, a system of criteria is needed that would proceed from the gradation of errors based on the degree of distortion of the original content during translation.
 - ❖ Main types of errors:
 - ❖ which represent a gross distortion of the content; as a result, the translation indicates a completely different situation and actually misinforms the receptor;
 - ❖ leading to inaccurate transmission of the original meaning, but not completely distorting it – the translation describes the same situation as in the original, but its individual details are not specified accurately enough. For example:

He was one of the best British football players in 1950's. – In 1950, he was one of the best footballers in England. Translator did not pay attention to the plural formant when naming the year in the original – "fifties".

They do not violate the general meaning of the original, but reduce the quality of the translation text due to deviations from the stylistic norms of the translating

language, the use of units that are not widely used in this type of text, the abuse of foreign language borrowings or technical jargon, etc.

Violations of the mandatory norms of the translation language that do not affect the equivalence of the translation, but indicate that the translator is not sufficiently proficient in this language or is unable to overcome the influence of the original language. When evaluating the quality of a particular translation on the usual five-point scale, errors of these types are assigned a certain "estimated weight".

For example:

Each error of the first type reduces the overall score of the translation by one point, the second-by half a point, and errors of the third and fourth types will affect the score only if they are not isolated, but typical, and then they collectively reduce the score by another half point. These standards correspond to a certain amount (of translation material – if the volume is large, a corresponding recalculation is made.

Such criteria are, of course, conditional. They may include additional coefficients depending on the importance of the materials being translated and the type of translation.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Fedorov A.V. Fundamentals of the general theory of translation. Moscow: 1983, 197 p.
2. Chernov G. V. Theory and practice of simultaneous translation. Moscow: 1987, 137 p.
3. Nuritdinova Y.A. The use of multimedia presentations when learning English. International scientific journal. Economy and society. № 6(73) -s.: 2020.